

ISic3409

I.Sicily inscription 3409

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

found in the pavement of Syracuse Cathedral

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140357

1. Εὐσεβ [ῆς]

2. καὶ #⁵⁶ Ἀγάθη

3. [ἔ]ζησεν ἔ [τη —]

4. [— —]M [— — —]

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644954

PHI 140357

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0059a (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
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Korhonen, K. 2002. Three cases of Greek/Latin imbalance in Roman Syracuse. In Ostenfeld, E.N.(eds.), *Greek Romans and Roman Greeks. Studies in cultural interaction.* Aarhus. pp. 70-80. At 78 n.21

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